

tracted to the light but did not enter the trap settled near it. Because moths are nocturnal, movement ceased after day-light.

We compared deadheart and whitehead incidence by selecting 10 hills in diagonal lines at 1, 5, 10, and 20 m from the trap, and in fields located far away from the light traps where the light could not be seen by YSB. As distance from the light trap increased, percent deadhearts declined (Table 2).

The increased infestation at 1 m around the trap was due to the settlement of YSB. Moths also may have migrated to surrounding areas during the day and caused more damage in that area as indicated by higher incidences even at the distance of 10 m. Our data indicate it may be wise to spray around the trap area with a suitable insecticide to reduce field damage. □

Table 1. Relation between light trap catch and settlement of YSB around the trap, Madurai, India.

Date	Moths settled (no./10 hills)	Light trap catch (no.)
8 Dec 1981	63	242
9 Dec 1981	71	387
10 Dec 1981	68	342
11 Dec 1981	61	288
12 Dec 1981	51	220
13 Dec 1981	97	620
14 Dec 1981	81	420
15 Dec 1981	88	580
16 Dec 1981	32	36
17 Dec 1981	28	42
18 Dec 1981	31	86
19 Dec 1981	48	108
20 Dec 1981	58	280
21 Dec 1981	73	460

$r = +0.79^{**a}$

^aSignificant at 1% level.

Table 2. YSB incidence at different distances from the light trap, Madurai, India.

Date	Incidence (%)				
	1 m	5 m	10 m	20 m	Light shadow region
15 Dec 1981	22	20	11	6	7
22 Dec 1981	36	24	18	13	14
29 Dec 1981	57	49	37	23	24
6 Jan 1982	59	50	39	25	27
13 Jan 1982	67	52	43	26	29
20 Jan 1982	74	55	46	29	32
24 Jan 1982	82	57	46	29	31
3 Feb 1982	86	21	14	12	13
10 Feb 1982	91	24	15	12	15
17 Feb 1982	100	28	18	15	17
Meananalysis	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄	T ₅

F = 24.07^{**a}
CD (P = 0.05) = 7.55

^aSignificant at 1% level.

Population density of *Sogatella furcifera* (Horvath) (WBPH) and *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stal.) (BPH)

K. Gunathilagaraj and S. Chelliah, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, India

We compared changes in population density of WBPH and BPH in the greenhouse at the Paddy Breeding Station, Coimbatore. In 4 experiments with 12 replications, combinations of WBPH and BPH were placed on individually caged 30-d-old potted TN1 plants as follows: 10 WBPH and 10 BPH first instar nymphs; 10 WBPH and 20 BPH; 20 WBPH and 10 BPH; and 1 WBPH and 1 BPH brachypterous female. Insect population was monitored for three generations.

WBPH population increased more rapidly than that of BPH in all the experiments (see figure). There was no significant difference in population level during the first 2 generations when 10 first-instar nymphs of both species and one brachypterous female of both species were confined together in different experiments. However, the differences were highly significant in experiments with different numbers of first-instar nymphs.

Population density of WBPH and BPH, Coimbatore, India.

WBPH and BPH populations declined after the second generation. Crop age may have favored the buildup of WBPH over BPH, because BPH population usually increases after heading. The field population of WBPH usually is largest 70-90 d after seeding, which corresponds roughly with the age of TN1 plants during the third generation in this experiment. □

Electronically recorded disturbances in the feeding behavior of green leafhopper (GLH) on neem oil-treated rice plants

R. C. Saxena, principal research scientist, International Centre of Insect Physiology and Ecology, Nairobi, Kenya, and associate entomologist, IIRRI; and Z. R. Khan, postdoctoral fellow, Entomology Department, IIRRI

We electronically recorded aberrations in GLH feeding behavior on neem oil-treated rice plants.

A fine (1.8 mμ), 5-cm-long gold wire was attached by silver paint to the dorsum of an 8- to 10-h-old GLH female. The insect was starved for 2 h and then its normal feeding activity was recorded electronically for 180 min using a D. C.